

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL RESOURCES OF WESTERN AZERBAIJAN IN THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the interpretation of Western Azerbaijan's historical and cultural heritage within the social environment and explores its role in shaping the community's mindset. The study emphasizes the threat of losing this heritage and underlines the importance of its preservation. It is well known that elements such as historical monuments, literature, art staff, philosophical traditions, and the local language have always influenced the formation of the region's social environment.

Keywords: Western Azerbaijan, historical and cultural heritage, resources, social environment, society

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INTRODUCTION

Western Azerbaijan is a region rich in historical and cultural heritage, and this richness plays a significant role in shaping its social and cultural life. The centuries-old history, cultural traditions, customs, and the diverse legacies of different parts of this region have significantly influenced the mindset and social structure of the local population. The historical and cultural resources of Western Azerbaijan are not only a reflection of the region's peoples but also key factors in shaping their worldview, social relations, and other fundamental aspects of society.

The cultural heritage of the region reflects not only the way of life of the peoples who once lived there but also the deeper social dynamics that have determined collective modes of thinking and behavior. Historical monuments, literature, works of art, religious and philosophical traditions, as well as the local language and culture, have been foundational in the formation of Western Azerbaijan's social environment and collective consciousness. Unfortunately, these territories currently do not fall within the administrative control of our Republic, which hinders efforts to preserve and transmit this heritage to future generations. However, interpreting this legacy is not only essential for understanding the past, but also for clarifying the present situation and future prospects. It is believed that preserving and eventually restoring this heritage will greatly contribute to the region's social and cultural development. The relevance of this article stems precisely from these issues.

The aim of the present article is to analyze the importance of Western Azerbaijan's historical and cultural resources in the social environment and to explore their impact on the society's system of thought. Fur-

thermore, conducting such an analysis is crucial for understanding the directions of social development and anticipating future transformations in the social environment.

The object of research in this article is the historical and cultural resources that have played a central role in the society of Western Azerbaijan. The subject of the study is the interpretation of these resources within the social context.

The scientific novelty lies in the examination of how the historical traces of territories currently beyond our national borders influence social and cultural development, and in emphasizing the role of this influence in shaping thought and behavior patterns within society. At the same time, the study introduces modern approaches related to the restoration of the social and cultural heritage of the occupied region, thereby offering a new perspective to ongoing academic discussions. This also provides a foundation for the development of effective policies and initiatives aimed at the region's future advancement. Such an approach considers Western Azerbaijan's historical and cultural heritage not only as a relic of the past, but also as a living influence on both the present and the future.

1. THE SOCIO-CULTURAL LIFE OF WESTERN AZERBAIJAN

As is well known, historical and cultural resources are among the fundamental factors shaping the collective memory and identity of any society. The interpretation of these resources within the social environment serves the preservation of public values and their transmission to future generations. In this context, historical monuments, examples of cultural heritage, and elements of folklore play a crucial role in the process of self-awareness among individuals. The interpretation of such resources is not only aimed at enhancing historical knowledge but also at reinforcing social cohesion. Therefore, the proper interpretation of historical and cultural resources ensures the sustainability of social development and cultural diversity.

Based on available scholarly sources regarding the period of Western Azerbaijan, this article seeks to uncover the relationship between historical-cultural resources and the social environment. With its rich historical and cultural heritage, Western Azerbaijan has also maintained a vibrant socio-cultural environment. Although the region was politically separated from the Republic of Azerbaijan due to occupation in the 20th century, various social and cultural activities continued in an effort to preserve and sustain the local culture. Traditional crafts, music, dance, and language have served as the foundational pillars of the region's socio-cultural life.

However, in modern times, the distortion of this rich heritage and the transformation of the social environment have emerged as key factors influencing the identity and self-perception of the local population.

The first section of the article explores the socio-cultural life of the indigenous population that once lived in Western Azerbaijan. This section examines topics such as domestic life and housing, the population's engagement in crafts and agriculture, family and household culture, and education.

1.1. Domestic Culture

The residential environment of the Western Azerbaijan region reflected elements of traditional Azerbaijani home culture. The architectural structure of the houses in the area clearly demonstrates this influence. As is well known, a house is a basic necessity for human life and often serves as an expression of traditional craftsmanship. In Western Azerbaijan, especially in the Goycha district, houses commonly referred to by locals as *garadam* were constructed.

These dwellings were built using technologies suited to local needs and climate. They featured built-in niches used for storing household items, serving the function of shelves; *tandır* ovens that replaced heating systems and were also used for baking bread; fences woven from reeds (*chatan*) enclosing the yard area; and separate structures built for keeping livestock. Typically, the houses had no more than two rooms - one served as a bedroom for the head of the household, and the other functioned as a guest room. Due to the lack of electricity, lighting was provided using oil lamps known as *chira*.

In later periods, the *garadam* evolved to be used for food storage and also functioned as a kitchen. Additionally, a small utility room called *kilar* was built adjacent to the *garadam*, serving the role of a refrigerator. In some households, especially in the *Vedibasari* region, each home had its own food storage shed, locally referred to as *yandam* [Nasibov, 2019, p. 109-111; Alakbarli, 2003, p.139-140].

1.2. Occupation of the Local Population

In Western Azerbaijan, agriculture was the primary occupation for a large portion of the population. In crop farming, a variety of grains were cultivated, including barley (six-rowed barley, white barley, sword barley, black barley, fine wheat, butter wheat, spring red wheat, and Karabakh wheat), tobacco, cotton, vegetables (beans, cabbage, onions, garlic, carrots, beets, cucumbers, peas), and fruits (including apple varieties such as *Vahab*, *Kerbelayi*, *Hajihuseynali Jafar*, pear varieties like *Malacha*, *Hajimehdi*, winter pear, and

plums, cherries, apricots, peaches, quinces, mulberries, black currants, yellow currants, walnuts, and grapes).

The local population in Western Azerbaijan also raised a variety of livestock, including cows, sheep, goats, horses, oxen, mules, camels, chickens, ducks, geese, and turkeys. Typically, livestock such as cows, sheep, and goats were used for meat, milk, and wool, while horses, mules, oxen, and camels served as transportation and draft animals. Among these animals, camels played a particularly important role in transportation, especially in the *Zengibasari* district where camel caravans were used as a primary means of freight transportation. These caravans were led by three main leaders, known as *gatarbashi* (train leader), while the overall leader of the caravan was called *karvanbashi*.

In the *Sadenagac* village of the *Goycha* district, beekeeping was a significant activity, providing the region with honey. It was common for each household to have beehives in their yard, and well-known beekeepers included *Qeshem Ibrahim oglu*, *Zeynalabdi Mukhtar oglu*, *Zeynalabdi Mesmali oglu*, *Mammadkhan Nesib oglu*, and *Shura Mammad oglu* [Nasibov, 2019, p.112-119; Alakbarli, 2002, p.67-68; Alakbarli, 2003, p. 129].

Western Azerbaijan was also known for its craftsmanship. Various traditional trades developed in the region, such as blacksmithing (in the *Sadenagac* village of *Goycha*), copper-smithing (in the *Sadenagac* village of *Goycha*), soap-making (in the *Gernibasari* district), dyeing (in the *Irevan*, *Zengibasari*, and *Gernibasari* districts), and carpet weaving (in the *Sadenagac* village of *Goycha*). In blacksmithing, tools for household and agricultural use, such as axes, hoes, shovels, knives, sickles, and hammers, were crafted in local forges. Blacksmiths such as *Mashadi Mammadvali Mirza oglu*, *Molokan Fyodor*, *Eyvaz Sayad oglu*, and *Giyas Mursal oglu* were noted for their skill in this trade. Soap-making was a major industry in the *Gernibasari* district, and it reached such a level of production that merchants in *Irevan* faced restrictions on selling local soap in the city, as stated by *I. Shopen*. Carpet weaving and silk production were also highly important crafts in the region. Women involved in these industries produced various household textiles, including quilts, mattresses, cushions, saddlebags, and carpets. Dyes were derived from natural sources such as walnut skins, onion skins, yarrow, and green walnut shells, with vibrant colors like red, blue, green, and dark yellow being commonly used, along with motifs of mythical creatures, camels, and caravan symbols [Nasibov, 2019, p.119-123; Alakbarli, 2002, p. 69].

Furthermore, the region had knowledgeable individuals who were involved in traditional medicine. These included bone setters like *Hajimahammad oglu Mashadagha*, *Mammadova Gismat Mashadagha gizi*, *Mammadov Ali Mashadagha oglu*, *Huseynov Huseyn Aghamirza oglu*, *Terpli İdris*, and *Sinigchi Hasi*, as well as herbalists such as *Horslu Sheshe arvad*, *Shahbazov Jalal*, and *Daghdalanli Pari gari*, who were known for their use of medicinal plants [Mirzayev, 2004, p. 734-735].

Western Azerbaijan was also a center for the *Ashiq* (minstrel) tradition. Notable *Ashiqs* from the region included *Ashiq Jalil*, *Ashiq Gulu*, *Ashiq Khalaf*,

Ashiq Bilal, Ashiq Agha, Ashiq Ahmed, Ashiq Kerem, Ashiq Allahverdi Ismayil oglu, Ashiq Pasha, Ashiq Zeynab, Ashiq Jabbar, and Ashiq Gurban. Musicians such as Khudayev Rajab Mammadali oglu (who played zurna and balaban), Shirinov Shirin Ali oglu (who played zurna and drum), Mammadov Gafar Agakishi oglu (who played drum), Allahverdiyev Garkez Khanlar oglu (who played zurna and balaban), Hummetov Mammad Mikayil oglu (who played zurna and balaban), Ashiq Behbud Bashir oglu (who played saz, zurna, and balaban), Karimov Karim Mahammad oglu (who played black zurna, clarinet, and drum), Gazanfar Pasha oglu (who played kamancha), Siyanfar Pasha oglu (who played qaval), Balabanchi Bahman, and Aghayarov Selim (singer and song performer) also contributed to the musical heritage of the region [Mirzayev, 2004, p. 730-732].

1.3. Educational Culture

Education played a crucial role in the development of the social and cultural life of Western Azerbaijan. In the early days, education took place in madrassas and mullah houses, and later in schools attached to mosques. Classes were typically taught by mullahs. Over time, formal schools were established. Before the conquest of the Irevan Khanate, some khans would send their people to educational institutions and religious centers in Iran, Turkey, and the Middle East, as well as to Russia and Europe for further studies. However, after the Russian conquest, the issue of education in Russian and European schools became more prominent. The first modern Russian-Tatar school in the Vedibaslar district was opened in 1883 in the village of Boyuk Vedi through the efforts of the intellectual Agasi Suleymanov. In the Sadenagac village of the Goycha district, the first primary school was established in 1930. In 1881, the Irevan Gymnasium, the Irevan Teachers' Seminary, and the Uluxanlı school began their operations in the city of Irevan. However, both the Irevan Gymnasium and the Irevan Teachers' Seminary were closed on August 6, 1918, as a result of the catastrophic events caused by the Armenians. These schools offered lessons in Islamic law, native language, Russian language, arithmetic, geography, history, literature, and drawing.

Another significant contribution to education was the local practice of sending a young person to study abroad via charitable efforts. Some examples include individuals sent to study in places such as Mashad, Najaf, Haji Akhund, Haji Molla Imran, and Sheikh Safer Maharramzadeh. In general, the intellectuals of the time included figures such as Ismayil Huseynov, Huseyn Qurbanov, Ismayil Aliyev, Adil Jabbarov, Bayramali Mustafayev, Bayram Isayev, Alikhan Nabyev, Hasan Rzayev, Ibrahim Jafarov, Isakh Shabanov, Iskander Hajiyev, Ziyad Keremov, Mayil Jafarov, Musa Ilyasov, Rahim Imamaliyev, Tahir Rahimov, Safar Safarov, Shamsaddin bey Mahmudbeyov, Farenza bey Mahmudbeyov, Agamirza Suleymanov, Mirza Nasruddin Shadtinski, Abbasgulu bey Shadtinski, Teymur bey Shadtinski, Sheikhuddin Suleymanov, Mohammad Maharramov, Alekberbey Qadimbeyov, Mehdi bey Melikaslanov, Mirabbas Mirbagirzadeh, Akbar Agha Sheikhuislamov, Miryusif

Mirbabayev, Taji Khanim Qaziyeva, Ruqiyya and Kubra Khanim sisters, and Academician Ahmed Rajabli, among others [Nasibov, 2019, p.128-129; Alakbarli, 2003, p.145-146; Zeynalov, 2011, p.6, p.10-20]. The presence of women among the educated individuals was a particularly important step for the advancement of knowledge.

Speaking of intellectuals, it is also important to mention the press activities in Western Azerbaijan. Newspapers and journals such as Chelak (1882), Irevan Herald (1911), Laklak (1914), Burkhani-Haqiqat, Youth Council (1917), Ranjbar (1922), Communist (1922-1923), Zangi (1924-1927), Golden Dawn (1927-1937), Communist (1937-1939), Soviet Armenia (1939-1989) played a significant role in the region's intellectual and cultural life [https://anl.az/el/emb/Qerbi_Azerbaycan/menbeler.htm].

1.4. Family and Household Culture

The family and household culture of Western Azerbaijan reflects key elements of Azerbaijani cultural heritage. Traditional values such as the observance of national and religious ceremonies, the high regard for family values, and the deep respect and care shown toward women highlight the region's enduring cultural identity. Celebrations and rituals such as Khidir Nabi, Novruz, Ramadan, Muharram, animal sacrifice (Qurbankesme), weddings, and mourning ceremonies were integral parts of daily life, with each occasion involving careful and deliberate preparation by the local population.

During these ceremonies, special meals were prepared for guests, and gatherings were organized in accordance with the nature of the event. Wedding ceremonies, in particular, followed deeply rooted customs and were preceded by lengthy preparation processes. The rituals included bringing the bride into the household and hosting a wedding feast, each stage carried out with symbolic and ceremonial practices. Mourning ceremonies also held significant cultural weight, as they served as moments for family members to unite, share grief, and express solidarity during times of loss.

These traditions illustrate the depth of the region's cultural fabric and its strong connection to ancient customs, highlighting how Western Azerbaijan maintained and preserved its heritage across generations [https://anl.az/el/emb/Qerbi_Azerbaycan_en/merasim.htm].

2. THE ROLE OF HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL RESOURCES IN SHAPING THE THOUGHT PATTERNS OF WESTERN AZERBAIJANI SOCIETY

2.1 Interpretation of Historical and Cultural Resources in the Social Thought of the Community

The historical and cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan has significantly shaped the intellectual framework of the community across different periods. This region, situated at the crossroads of ancient civilizations and historic states, has been deeply influenced by various socio-political developments that have, in turn, molded its collective thinking and identity.

Based on historical and academic analysis, the following factors have played a substantial role in shaping the social mindset in Western Azerbaijan:

- ✓ historical conditions;
- ✓ education;
- ✓ cultural resources;
- ✓ religious worldview;
- ✓ customs and traditions;
- ✓ folklore;
- ✓ family values and social relations;
- ✓ the synthesis of history and culture;
- ✓ multicultural values, etc.

These elements directly influenced the population, shaping their way of life, creativity, and social expression. As a result, unique socio-cultural dynamics and a distinctive local cultural identity emerged. The artistic creativity, traditions, and practices developed by the people reflect a living cultural system rooted in historical continuity and collective memory.

2.2. The Impact of the Interpretation of Historical and Cultural Resources on the Tourism Sector

It is well established that historical and cultural resources are a product of a society's social thought. Every community possesses a unique cultural heritage derived from its history, traditions, and social values. This heritage not only shapes identity but also plays a critical role in societal development. Cultural values, customs, and the coexistence of diverse ethnic groups influence societal behaviors and perspectives.

Preservation and development of cultural heritage simultaneously support economic growth. This is particularly evident in tourism-related activities, which promote local craftsmanship and artisanal traditions. Cultural resources that define the lifestyle, ethnicity, and social norms of a community also have substantial impacts on its economic and social life. Heritage elements such as historical monuments, folklore, traditional customs, cuisine, and handicrafts form the foundation for tourism development.

Tourism can have both positive and negative impacts on culture. On the positive side, it promotes the preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage. On the negative side, it risks commodifying traditions and diluting authentic cultural expressions. Tourism can also lead to cultural conflicts or the assimilation of local cultures into a globalized identity.

The interconnection between cultural resources and tourism is critical: safeguarding heritage ensures both local well-being and sustainable tourism. While tourism is an irreplaceable medium for sharing culture with the world, excessive exploitation of these resources must be avoided.

In general, tourism's cultural impacts can be summarized as follows:

- socio-cultural influences;
- host-tourist interactions;
- intercultural exchanges;
- demographic changes;
- local attitudes toward tourism;
- impacts on cultural sustainability;
- both positive and negative outcomes [Akova and Atsiz, 2019].

As evident, culture, society, and tourism are deeply intertwined. The same potential exists in Western Azerbaijan, where a strong socio-cultural foundation could serve as a valuable asset for tourism. With appropriate management, tourism can become a force

that strengthens regional identity without harming the community's material and spiritual value systems.

CONCLUSION

The tourism potential of Western Azerbaijan, characterized by its rich historical, cultural, and natural resources, holds tremendous promise for the region's economic and social development. However, the area's prior occupation has severely hindered the full realization of this potential. Despite these challenges, the region's unique cultural heritage, ancient landmarks, and stunning natural landscapes remain a source of immense value, not only for the local population but also for the wider tourism industry.

Historical sites such as ancient cities, fortresses, and religious monuments offer a deep connection to the past, making the region a potential hotspot for cultural tourism. Similarly, the breathtaking natural landscapes, including mountains, rivers, and forests, have the capacity to attract eco-tourists, adventurers, and nature lovers from around the world. The region's biodiversity and unspoiled environments are assets that could significantly contribute to sustainable tourism development.

In conclusion, the future of Western Azerbaijan's tourism industry remains promising. In the future, projects to be implemented in this field will not only improve the living standards of the local population but also strengthen Western Azerbaijan's position in global tourism. In this regard, the proper use of the region's cultural-historical and natural resources is crucial for both economic development and the preservation of the region's culture. With careful planning, international cooperation, and peace-building efforts, the region can one day fully unlock its tourism potential, benefiting not only the local communities but also the global tourism sector as a whole.

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